

“FeatherStrong ElevBlock”

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Abstract

This Project, *Featherstrong Elevblock* , Addresses The Need For A Lightweight Yet High-Strength Structural Block Suitable For Elevated Construction Systems.

The Primary Objective Of This Research Is To Design And Develop A Lightweight Elevation Block That Offers Improved Reducing Structural Dead Load. The Project Focuses On Optimizing Material Composition Using *Plastic Waste* To Achieve A Balanced Combination Of Strength, Durability, And Reduced Density.

The Methodology Involved Material Selection, Mix Design Experimentation, Casting Of Prototype Blocks, And Compressive Strength Testing Using Standard Laboratory Procedures. Comparative Analysis Was Conducted Between Conventional Concrete Blocks And The Developed Feather Strong ElevBlock To Evaluate Performance Improvements.

Experimental Results Indicate A Significant Reduction In Block Weight While Maintaining Competitive Compressive Strength Within Structural Safety Limits. The Developed Block Demonstrates Potential For Cost Savings In Foundation Design And Improved Construction Efficiency.

Keywords

LDPE, Or Low-Density Polyethylene , Durable , Elevation Breeze Block , Lightweight , Environmental Impact.

Introduction

The Construction Industry Continuously Seeks Innovative Materials That Reduce Structural Load While Maintaining High Strength And Durability. Traditional Concrete Blocks Contribute Significantly To The Overall Weight Of Buildings, Increasing Foundation Costs And Limiting Elevation Flexibility.

This Project, *Featherstrong Elevblock* , Addresses The Need For A Lightweight Yet High-Strength Structural Block Suitable For Elevated Construction Systems.

The Primary Objective Of This Research Is To Design And Develop A Lightweight Elevation Block That Offers Improved Reducing Structural Dead Load. The Project Focuses On Optimizing Material Composition Using *Plastic Waste* To Achieve A Balanced Combination Of Strength, Durability, And Reduced Density.

Plastic Waste Refers To Discarded Plastic Materials That Are No Longer Useful Or Required. It Includes Items Such As Plastic Bottles, Bags, Packaging Materials, Containers, Straws, And Other Synthetic Products.

The Rapid Increase In Plastic Production And Consumption Has Led To Serious Environmental Problems. This Problem Also Overcome In This Project In Which We Can Add A Plastic Waste In Conventional Manufacturing Process Of A Elevation Block For Making Them A Light Weight, Which Is Their Disadvantage.

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Experimental Results Indicate A Significant Reduction In Block Weight While Maintaining Competitive Compressive Strength Within Structural Safety Limits. The Developed Block Demonstrates Potential For Cost Savings In Foundation Design And Improved Construction Efficiency.

In Conclusion, Featherstrong Elevblock Presents A Promising Solution For Lightweight Structural Applications, Contributing To Sustainable And Efficient Modern Construction Practices.

Scope Of Study

- To find economical solution for reduction dead load in construction material by adding waste product
- To utilize plastic waste from environment
- To provide eco-friendly solution of higher dead load of a Elevation Breeze block

Research Objective

The main objectives of this study are

- Weight Reduction

To Reduce The Overall Unit Weight Of Conventional Concrete Breeze Blocks By %.

To Use Lightweight Materials Such As Plastic Waste In Powder Form

- Structural Performance Evaluation

To Test Compressive Strength, Flexural Strength, And Durability.

To Ensure Structural Stability Under Wind Loads When Used As Elevation Screens.

- Sustainability Goals

To Incorporate Recycled Or Eco-Friendly Materials.

To Reduce Embodied Carbon And Overall Environmental Impact.

- Cost Effectiveness

To Ensure Production Cost Remains Competitive With Traditional Breeze Blocks.

Material used

The Materials Used For The Investigation Are Described With Respect To Their Sources And Relevant Physical And Chemical Properties.

The Main Ingredients Of Featherstrong Elevblock Are:

- Cement
- LDPE Material
- Grit (Coarse Aggregate)
- Water
- Pigment

FeatherStrong ElevBlock = Cement + LDPE material + Grit + Water + pigment

Experimental Methodology

The Experimental Investigation Was Carried Out To Evaluate The Suitability Of Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE) Waste Powder As A Partial Additive In The Production Of Decorative Elevation Blocks. Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC 43/53 Grade), Washed Sand (Bhogavo Reti), Grit As Coarse Aggregate, Pigment, And Potable Water Were Used As The Primary Constituents Of The Mix. LDPE Waste In Powdered Form Was Incorporated Into The Concrete Mixture At Varying Proportions Of 1%, 3%, And 5% By Weight Of Cement, Corresponding To 26 G, 78 G, And 130 G, Respectively. Initially, Cement, Sand, Pigment, And LDPE Powder Were Dry Mixed Thoroughly To Ensure Uniform Distribution Of Materials. Subsequently, Grit Was Added Gradually And Mixed Properly. Water Was Then Added Slowly While Maintaining A Water-Cement Ratio Between 0.4 And 0.5 To Obtain A Workable Mix. Mixing Was Performed Using A Drum Mixer Or Manually For Small-Scale Production.

Before Casting, The Moulds Were Cleaned And Prepared Using Steel Or HDPE Moulds Designed According To The Required Geometric Perforated Elevation Block Pattern. The Prepared Concrete Mix Was Poured Into The Moulds In Layers And Compacted Using A Table Vibrator With Light Vibration To Eliminate Entrapped Air And Ensure Proper Filling Of The Mould Cavities. After Casting, The Blocks Were Left Undisturbed For Initial Setting And Then Demoulded After 24 Hours. The Demoulded Specimens Were Cured In Water For 7, 14, And 28 Days To Achieve The

Desired Strength Development. Upon Completion Of Curing, The Blocks Were Tested For Physical And Mechanical Properties Such As Compressive Strength, Water Absorption, Density, And Visual Appearance. The Performance Of Blocks Containing Different Percentages Of LDPE Waste Was Compared With That Of Conventional Elevation Blocks To Determine The Optimum LDPE Content For Producing Sustainable, Aesthetically Appealing, And Structurally Adequate Elevation Blocks.

Table 1: Compressive strength

Specimen No.	Additive Replacement (%)	W/C Ratio	Compressive Strength (Mpa Or N/Mmm²)
1.	1% LDPE material	0.50	4.7 N/mm²
2.	3% LDPE material	0.57	5.2 N/mm²
3.	5% LDPE material	0.63	5.3 N/mm²

Conclusion

This Project, Featherstrong Elevblock, Addresses The Need For A Lightweight Yet High-Strength Structural Block Suitable For Elevated Construction Systems.

- Weight Reduction
- Structural Performance Evaluation
- Sustainability Goals
- Cost Effectiveness
- Ease Of Installation
- To Reduce Handling Difficulty Due To Lighter Weight.

- Reduces Structural Dead Load
- Supports Sustainable Construction Practices

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